

Overall study design

Title of the study	CSF sphingolipid levels are correlated with neuroinflammatory cytokines and differentiate neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder from multiple sclerosis		
Document creation date	04/19/2024	Corresponding Email	anthony.don@sydney.edu.au
Principle investigator	Anthony Don	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	The University of Sydney	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	1-phase system	Butanol/Methanol (1/1)
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	Low resolution
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Resolution at MS1	Unit
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Centroid mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.8
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
MS type	QQQ	Resolution at MS2	Unit
MS vendor	Thermo	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
Ion source	ESI	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS1, MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	No
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	Included as supplementary data	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Washington University Multiple Sclerosis and Nervous System Diseases Repository and Database. / Human / Other liquid material

Provided information	Freeze-thaw cycles	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	Yes
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

IRCCS Ospedale Maggiore Policlinico / Human / Other liquid material

Provided information	Freeze-thaw cycles	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	Yes
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
-FA1-NH3			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
TG(17:0/17:0/17:0)-FA1-NH3		for all TG(XX:X) (discovery cohort)	
TG(16:0/16:0/16:0)-FA1-NH3 d31		for all TG(XX:X) (validation cohort)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	HG(PC,184)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

2) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPC(17:0)	HG(PC,184)	For all LPC(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

3) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPE(17:1)	-HG(PE,141)	For all LPE(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

4) PA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

4) PA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PA(17:0/17:0)	FA1(+O)	For all PA(XX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

5) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No			
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No			
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold			
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes			
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No			
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No			
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>HG(PC,184)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FA1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	HG(PC,184)	FA1		
Fragment name						
HG(PC,184)						
FA1						
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1			
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing			
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes			
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A			
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-			

5) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PC(38:0)</td> <td>HG(PC,184)</td> <td>For all PC(XX:X)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	PC(38:0)	HG(PC,184)	For all PC(XX:X)		
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
PC(38:0)	HG(PC,184)	For all PC(XX:X)							
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	No								

6) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

6) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE(34:0)	-HG(PE,141)	For all PE(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

7) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

7) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE(34:0)	-HG(PE,141)	For all PEP(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

8) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

8) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PG(17:0/17:0)	FA2(+O)	For all PG(XX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

9) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

9) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PI(15:0/18:1-d7)	FA2(+O)	For all PI(XX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

10) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	FA1(+O)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

10) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PS(17:0/17:0)	FA1(+O)	For all PS(XX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	LCB(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cer(d18:1/17:0)	LCB(-H3O2)	For all Cer(dXX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

12) CerP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CerP	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	LCB(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

12) CerP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cer1P(d18:1/12:0)	LCB(-H3O2)	For all Cer1P(dXX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

13) GM3[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GM3	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	HG(NHex,290)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

13) GM3[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
GM3(d36:1-d5)	HG(NHex,290)	For all gangliosides(dXX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

14) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	LCB(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

14) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LacCer(d18:1/12:0) LCB(-HO)		For all Hex2Cer(dXX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

15) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	LCB(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

15) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
GluCer(d18:1/17:0)	LCB(-H3O2)	For all Hex-Cer(dXX:X/XX:X) (validation cohort)	
GluCer(d18:1/12:0)	LCB(-H3O2)	For all Hex-Cer(dXX:X/XX:X) (discovery cohort)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

16) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No			
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No			
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold			
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes			
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No			
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No			
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>HG(PC,184)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LCB(-H3O2)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Fragment name	HG(PC,184)	LCB(-H3O2)
Fragment name						
HG(PC,184)						
LCB(-H3O2)						
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1			
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing			
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes			
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A			
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-			

16) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>SM(d18:1/17:0)</td> <td>HG(PC,184)</td> <td>For all SM(dXX:X/XX:X)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	SM(d18:1/17:0)	HG(PC,184)	For all SM(dXX:X/XX:X)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
SM(d18:1/17:0)	HG(PC,184)	For all SM(dXX:X/XX:X)							
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	No								

17) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	Cholesterol-HO		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

17) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
CE(17:0)	Cholesterol-HO	For all CE(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

18) ST[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	LCB(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

18) ST[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
ST(d18:1/17:0)	LCB(-H3O2)	For all ST(dXX:X/XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

19) Cholesterol[M+H-H2O]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cholesterol	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H-H2O] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	-C15H28		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

19) Cholesterol[M+H-H2O]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cholesterol-d7	-C15H28	Cholesterol	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

20) AcCa[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	AcCa	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
-FA			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

20) AcCa[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
AcCa(16:0)-d3	-FA	For all AcCa(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

21) LPS[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
-(C3H5NO2,87)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

21) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPS(17:1)	-(C3H5NO2,87)	For all LPS(XX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

22) S1P[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	S1P	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
FA			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

22) S1P[M+H]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
S1P(d17:1)	FA	For all S1P(dXX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

23) Sph[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Sph	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	FA		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

23) Sph[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Sph(d17:1)	FA	For all Sph(dXX:X)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

24) PE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name	FA2(+O)		
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

24) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes		Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2		Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2			Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 5.1
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass		
PE(17:0/17:0)	FA2(+O)	For all PE(XX:X/XX:X) (discovery cohort)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount		Batch correction	No
Response correction	No		Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No			